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Inhibition of DNA synthesis in the transcription system of Taq DNA polymerase by various iron and cobalt(II) tris-dioximate clathrochelates: *in vitro* study and X-ray structure of leader inhibitors, the carboxyl-terminated macrobicyclic complexes[†]

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Abstract

A series of the iron and cobalt(II) mono- and bis-clathrochelates was *in vitro* tested in the transcription system of Taq DNA polymerase (DNAP), based on polymerase chain reaction. All these complexes were found to be micromolar transcription inhibitors, but only several clathrochelates with terminal biorelevant groups are inhibitors with IC₅₀ in a low micromolar range from 5 to 40 μM. Highest *in vitro* inhibitory activity is observed for the iron(II) monoclathrochelates with two carboxyphenylsulfide substituents. Their monofunctionalized analog and *ortho*-, *meta*- or *para*-heterofunctionalized morpholine-containing complexes with the single carboxyphenylsulfide substituent showed a substantially less inhibitory activity. The former iron(II) monoclathrochelates are also more active inhibitors

[†] Other authors dedicate this paper to the memory of Prof. O. Varzatskii who suddenly passed away on 20 December 2017

than their bis-cages analogs, the monoclatrochelates with two carboxyl-terminated alkylsulfide groups and those with pyridyl- or morpholyl-terminated alkylamine ribbed substituents. Concentration- and structure-dependent *in vitro* inhibitory activities of mono- and bis-clathrochelates in the system of DNAP are from one to two orders of magnitude lower than those for T7 RNAP. So, the selectivity of an inhibition of RNA synthesis, as compared with that of DNA, by the cage complexes under study is observed; the reasons of the observed DNA synthesis inhibition are discussed. The single crystal X-ray diffraction experiments for the leader di- and hexacarboxyl-terminated clathrochelate inhibitors of these polymerases were performed. In the crystal of a hexafunctionalized complex, the orientation of its ribbed substituents was found to be strongly affected by H-bonding of its terminal carboxyl groups; all of them give a very specific supramolecular motif through the formation of the O–H...O-bonded dimeric associates. Each molecule is H-bonded through two pairs of the O–H...O bonds with three macrobicycles, playing a role of the three-connected node. In the crystal of a dicarboxyl-terminated iron(II) clathrochelate, two macrobicyclic molecules in its asymmetric unit cell have an almost coplanar orientation of their arylsulfide ribbed substituents caused by strong H-bonding between their carboxyl groups, forming a clathrochelate dimer. Molecular surfaces of these carboxyl-terminated clathrochelates were analyzed using the Hirshfield and Voronoi approaches, suggesting that both the hydrophobic and hydrophilic interactions play a key role in the crystal packings and their molecules can form H-bonded assemblies and arrays with protein macromolecules.

Keywords

Drug design; DNA polymerase; Inhibitors; Clathrochelates; XRD structures; Hydrogen bonding

Introduction

Cage metal complexes (clathrochelates [1, 2]) have been recently recognized as prospective biological effectors (including so-called “topological drugs”) using

these three-dimensional species as rigid scaffolds for macromolecular binding. Designed clathrochelate molecules can form multicentered supramolecular interactions in the vacant cavities of protein macromolecules and(or) their macromolecular complexes, as well as on their surface, thus allowing to fight various viral and tumor diseases, neurodegenerative disorders, diabetes and amyloidosis. In particular, the ribbed-functionalized iron(II) clathrochelates are described as prospective transcription inhibitors of T7 RNA polymerase (RNAP) and antifibrillogenic agents due to their ability as guests to bind with proteins and their macromolecular complexes as hosts, thus forming the strong supramolecular host–guest assemblies; main results in the above fields have been recently highlighted [3]. Very recently, based on *in vitro* studies, we found [4] that an iron(II) hexachloroclathrochelate exhibits the substantial cytotoxicity and a high selectivity (as compared with normal cells) in human promyelocytic leukemia cells. On the other hand it seems to be very important to compare an inhibitory activity of the cage and bis-cage complexes of various types in the transcription system of RNAP [5] with that in the systems of other nuclear acids, such as DNA. Indeed, the presence or the absence of a selectivity of the inhibition of these superimposed (in a living body) biological processes seems to be a very important from the point of view of modern drug design. Taq DNA polymerase (DNAP, [6, 7]) is known to consist of a single polypeptide with a molecular weight of approximately 94 kDa. It synthesizes DNA at elevated temperatures from single-stranded templates in the presence of primer and this thermostable polymerase is frequently used in polymerase chain reaction (PCR). Here, we report the results of *in vitro* testing of a wide range of the iron and cobalt(II) cage complexes as the effectors in the transcription system of DNAP, as well as the single crystal X-ray structures of two of its leader transcription inhibitors, suitable for further computation studies of the above “clathrochelate – protein – nucleic acid” supramolecular complexes.

Experimental

The iron and cobalt(II) cage complexes under study shown in Scheme 1 were obtained as described elsewhere (see Refs. 8 – 17) for the detailed synthetic protocols). An inhibitory activity these clathrochelates against DNAP was tested *in vitro* using the standard procedures [18 – 20].

PCR assays: Real-Time PCRs were performed on CFX96™ Real-Time PCR system (BioRad, USA). Primers and the probes described [20] for the detection of soybean DNA were used. These primers, Lec1F (5'-TCC ACC CCC ATC CAC ATT T-3') and Lec1R (5'-GGC ATA GAA GGT GAA GTT GAA GGA-3'), delimit a 81 bp DNA segment from the soybean *lec1* gene (GenBank accession no K00821.1). Fluorogenic Lec1P probe, 5'-AAC CGG TAG CGT TGC CAG CTT CG -3', was labeled at its 5'-end with HEX (hexachlorofluorescein) as a reporter dye and at its 3'-end with BHQ1 (30-Black Hole Quencher 1) as a quencher.

Each 20 µl of the reaction mixture contained 10 mM of Tris-HCl buffer solution (pH 8.3), 50 mM of KCl, 2.5 mM of MgCl₂, 0.2 mM of each dNTP, 5 pmol of each a primer, 2.5 pmol of a probe, 1 U of DNAP (Thermo Scientific™, USA), and 2 µl of DNA template.

The temperature profile for the amplification consisted of an initial denaturation at 94°C for 3 min, followed by 45 cycles of a denaturation at 95°C for 15 s and by the primers annealing, and the synthesis at 60°C for 40 s. Fluorescence signal was measured after a primer annealing and the synthesis step in each amplification cycle. Amplification results were presented as threshold cycle (Ct) values. Threshold cycle for each sample was the cycle in which a kinetic curve of fluorescence crossed the threshold line. The inhibition *in vitro* experiments were performed using a variation of the concentration of a clathrochelate under study; the control experiments were performed in the same systems with an addition of the same amounts of DMSO, but without an addition of a clathrochelate inhibitor. All the assayed clathrochelate complexes under study were dissolved in a pure DMSO. 0.8 µl of a stock DMSO solution was added to a probe, thus giving the final concentrations of a macrobicyclic effector in the reaction mixture from 5 to 120 µM. IC₅₀ values were

calculated using a diagram of relation of the Ct values, characterizing an activity of DNAP, *versus* a concentration of a clathrochelate complex under study. An addition of DMSO into the above reaction mixture in its concentration up to 5 vol. % was found do not affect an activity of DNAP.

X-ray Crystallography

Single crystals of the complex $\text{Fe}((\text{meta-HOOC}\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{S})_2\text{Gm})_3(\text{Bn-C}_4\text{H}_9)_2$ (**1**) were grown from its saturated solution in an acetone – benzene 1:3 mixture by slow evaporation at room temperature. The red-plate crystal of $\text{C}_{56}\text{H}_{47}\text{B}_2\text{FeN}_6\text{O}_{18}\text{S}_6$ ($M = 1362.83$) is triclinic; at 120 K: $a = 10.9899(7)$, $b = 17.6868(14)$, $c = 17.9241(12)$ Å, $\alpha = 118.551(5)$, $\beta = 100.694(5)$, $\gamma = 90.810(5)^\circ$, $V = 2985.8(4)$ Å³, space group $P\bar{1}$, $Z = 2$, $D_{\text{calcd.}} = 1.516$ g cm⁻³, $\mu = 4.654$ mm⁻¹. The intensities of 14932 reflections were measured with a Bruker Apex II CCD diffractometer using Cu – K α radiation with multilayer optics ($\lambda = 1.54178$ Å). Single crystals of the complex $\text{FeBd}_2((\text{meta-HOOC}\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{S})_2\text{Gm})(\text{BF})_2 \cdot 0.75\text{C}_3\text{H}_6\text{O}$ (**2**·0.75C₃H₆O) were grown from its saturated solution in an acetone – benzene 1:5 mixture at room temperature. The dark-red prismatic single crystal of $\text{C}_{46.25}\text{H}_{34.5}\text{B}_2\text{F}_2\text{FeN}_6\text{O}_{10.75}\text{S}_2$ ($M = 1025.89$) is triclinic; at 100.0(1) K $a = 12.4070(15)$, $b = 19.114(2)$, $c = 19.548(2)$ Å, $\alpha = 91.033(3)$, $\beta = 92.246(3)$, $\gamma = 90.094(3)^\circ$, $V = 4631.4(10)$ Å³, space group $P\bar{1}$, $Z = 4$, $D_{\text{calcd.}} = 1.471$ g cm⁻³, $\mu = 0.491$ mm⁻¹. The intensities of 21105 reflections were measured with a Bruker Apex II CCD diffractometer using Mo – K α radiation with graphite monochromator ($\lambda = 0.71073$ Å).

The structures were solved by the direct method and refined by full-matrix least squares against F^2 . Non-hydrogen atoms were refined in anisotropic approximation except one equiprobably disordered *n*-butyl group of **1** and one equiprobable disordered acetone molecule of **2**·0.75C₃H₆O. Positions of the H(C) atoms were calculated and those of six and two H(O) atoms, respectively, were found from Fourier maps. All hydrogen atoms were included in the refinement by the riding

model with $U_{iso}(H) = nU_{eq}(X)$, where $n = 1.5$ for methyl and hydroxyl groups and 1.2 for the other atoms. For the crystal **1**, the refinement converged to $R1 = 0.0704$ for 5065 observed reflections with $I > 2\sigma(I)$; $wR2$ and GOF were 0.1937 and 1.01 for 8335 independent reflections. For the crystal **2**·0.75C₃H₆O, the refinement converged to $R1 = 0.0751$ for 14379 observed reflections with $I > 2\sigma(I)$ and $wR2$ and GOF were 0.1938 and 1.05 for 21105 independent reflections. All calculations were made using the SHELXL-2015 [21] and OLEX2 [22] program packages. The single crystal **2**·0.75C₃H₆O was twin with two components separated using PLATON package [23] and refined with combination of BASF/HKLF 5 instructions.

CCDC 1589221 and 1589222 contain the supplementary crystallographic data for this paper. These data can be obtained free of charge via <http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/conts/retrieving.html>.

Results and Discussion

In vitro study of inhibition of DNA synthesis, catalyzed by DNAP

A series of the iron and cobalt(II) mono- and bis-clathrochelates shown in Figure 1 was *in vitro* tested in the transcription system of DNAP, based on polymerase chain reaction; the data obtained are collected in Table 1. All the cage complexes under study were found to be micromolar transcription inhibitors in this system, but only several clathrochelates with terminal biorelevant groups are inhibitors with IC_{50} in a low micromolar range from 5 to 40 μ M. Highest *in vitro* inhibitory activity in the transcription system of DNAP was found for the monoribbed-functionalized iron(II) monoclathrochelates with two carboxyphenylsulfide ribbed substituents in *vic*-position of the same α -dioximate chelate fragment. Their monofunctionalized monomethinoclathrochelate analog, as well as the heterofunctionalized morpholine-containing cage complexes with the single carboxyphenylsulfide substituent possess a substantially less inhibitory activity, as compared with the above difunctionalized *ortho*-, *meta*- or *para*-carboxyphenylsulfide macrobicyclic complexes. These

iron(II) monoclathrochelates are more active inhibitors in the transcription system under study than their bis-clathrochelate analogs and the monoribbed-functionalized macrobicyclic iron(II) bis- α -benzildioximate with carboxyl-terminated alkylsulfide substituent. The above dicarboxyl-terminated clathrochelates are also substantially more active than the monoribbed-functionalized iron(II) complexes with two pyridyl- or morpholyl-terminated alkylamine ribbed substituents. On the other hand, passing from the dicarboxyl-terminated phenylsulfide macrobicyclic complexes to their hexacarboxyl-containing analogs does not substantially affect the IC_{50} values: for both these series of the clathrochelate inhibitors of DNA synthesis in the transcription system of DNAP, the same orders of their magnitudes are observed, thus not allowing the correct discussion of a decrease IC_{50} values within the below series of their constitutional isomers: for dicarboxyl-containing complexes in a row $meta_2 > para_2 > ortho_2$ and for their hexacarboxyl-terminated analogs in a row $ortho_6 > meta_6 > para_6$. In general, as can be seen from Table 1, *in vitro* inhibitory activities of the mono- and bis-clathrochelate inhibitors under study in the transcription system of DNAP are from one to two orders of magnitude lower than those in the transcription system of RNAP [5], thus suggesting that the selectivity of an inhibition of RNA synthesis, as compared with an inhibition of DNA synthesis, by the clathrochelates and bis-clathrochelates under study is observed. On the other hand, these cage complexes have demonstrated structure and concentration – dependent inhibition in their inhibitory activity. These cage complexes have demonstrated structure- and concentration-dependent inhibition in other transcription assays.

Towards the reasons of DNA synthesis inhibition

The modern trends in drug development lead to discovery of the new biological targets, including the hidden allosteric sites or the interfaces of macromolecular interactions. The concept of “topological drugs” [3] suggests the use of three-dimensional species as rigid scaffolds for macromolecular binding that form multicentered supramolecular interactions in the vacant cavities of protein

macromolecules and(or) their macromolecular complexes, as well as on their surfaces. Indeed, several examples of very efficient transcription inhibition by the designed iron(II) cage and bis-cage complexes with carboxyl-terminated ribbed substituents have been earlier reported [3, 5] for a model *in vitro* system based on a RNAP. Their inhibition mode has been deduced [3, 5] using experimental preincubation data and molecular docking calculations: the rigid and bulky three-dimensional inhibitor molecule is located in the same region of a supramolecular complex between the macromolecules of RNAP, of a matrix DNA and of a RNA synthesized, forming the intermolecular contacts with all of them. As a result, their inhibitory activity is affected not only by a geometric complementarity between these clathrochelate guests and the above pockets as hosts, but also by an ability of the peripheral and terminal groups in the apical and ribbed substituents of their macropolycyclic molecules to supramolecular binding with hydrophobic and hydrophilic fragments of the corresponding macromolecules forming the above hosting site [3, 24]. In particular, the data of [24] suggest a high impact of the electrostatic (polar) interactions of the terminal carboxyl groups of the ribbed-functionalized macrobicyclic effectors with the charged side groups of the complimentary aminoacid residues of a protein macromolecule in the formation of their supramolecular host – guest assemblies, formed *via* the multiple aromatic (stacking) interactions, hydrogen bonding and the dispersion interactions as well. These interactions are strongly affected by the positions of these carboxyl groups in the ribbed substituents of a clathrochelate molecule.

On the other hand, the above transcription inhibition mode in the system of RNAP is based on the formation of a dynamic clathrochelate-containing macromolecular assembly, that includes also a formed RNA [3, 5]. So, such assembly could not be isolated in its individual form that can give the crystals suitable for single crystal X-ray diffraction experiment. Moreover, even the experimental X-ray structure of a macromolecular complex of DNAP with a given primer (see Experimental part) is not yet described in literature. Therefore, the

computation experiments of a very high level should be performed to evaluate an inhibition mode of the leader clathrochelate inhibitors in the transcription system of DNAP. Such theoretical calculations are typically based on the known structures of the inhibitor molecules, which have been initially obtained using various experimental techniques (mainly, by single crystal X-ray diffraction). We succeeded to grow the single crystals of two of the leader carboxyl-terminated clathrochelate inhibitors in the transcription systems of both the above polymerases, which were suitable for the X-ray diffraction experiments (*vide infra*).

Crystal and molecular structures of the di- and hexacarboxyl-terminated iron(II) clathrochelates, the low micromolar and submicromolar DNAP and RNAP transcription inhibitors

Molecular structure of the clathrochelate $\text{Fe}((\text{meta-HOOC}\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{S})_2\text{Gm})_3(\text{Bn-C}_4\text{H}_9)_2$ is shown in Fig. 2; main geometrical parameters of its macrobicyclic framework, as well as those for two other *n*-butylboron-capped iron(II) hexaarylsulfide clathrochelates (Scheme 1, **3** and **4**) are listed in Table 2. In the former cage complex, the encapsulated iron(II) ion is situated in the centre of its FeN_6 -coordination polyhedron having the geometry intermediate between a trigonal prism (TP, the distortion angle $\varphi = 0^\circ$) and a trigonal antiprism (TAP, $\varphi = 60^\circ$); the corresponding angle φ is equal to 22.8° . This value is lower than those for the hexaarylsulfide iron(II) clathrochelates $\text{Fe}((\text{PIS})_2\text{Gm})_3(\text{Bn-C}_4\text{H}_9)_2$ and $\text{Fe}((\text{CF}_3\text{C}_6\text{F}_4\text{S})_2\text{Gm})_3(\text{Bn-C}_4\text{H}_9)_2$ shown in Scheme 1 (27.1 and 25.2° , respectively, Table 2); other geometrical parameters of their macrobicyclic frameworks are similar. At the same time, the overall molecular shapes of the above macrobicycles are very different. Indeed, the presence of six single C–S bonds allows a free rotation of these aromatic ribbed substituents at a cage framework that is restricted only by sterical clashes between them. For the crystals $\text{Fe}((\text{CF}_3\text{C}_6\text{F}_4\text{S})_2\text{Gm})_3(\text{Bn-C}_4\text{H}_9)_2$ and $\text{Fe}((\text{PIS})_2\text{Gm})_3(\text{Bn-C}_4\text{H}_9)_2$, which are formed mainly by hydrophobic intermolecular interactions (in the latter case, the terminal hydroxyl groups of phenolsulfide substituents are protected from a strong hydrogen bonding by two

bulky *tert*-butyl groups), their arylsulfide ribbed substituents in *vic*-position of the same chelate fragment are oriented antiparallel to each other and the PI-S (or $\text{CF}_3\text{C}_6\text{F}_4\text{-S}$) bonds in one of their boron-capped tripodal fragments are turned a clockwise, while the bonds of this type in the second fragment of this type are turned an anticlockwise to minimize the sterical clashes. In the molecule $\text{Fe}((\text{meta-HOCC}_6\text{H}_4\text{S})_2\text{Gm})_3(\text{Bn-C}_4\text{H}_9)_2$, an antiparallel orientation of its arylsulfide substituents is observed only in two of the three ribbed fragments, while the C-S bonds of *vic*-arylsulfide substituents are parallel in the third chelate moiety and the mean planes of their aromatic rings are almost coplanar (Fig. 2, **b**). So, the orientation of the ribbed substituents at a cage framework of the above molecule is strongly affected by hydrogen bonding of its terminal carboxyl groups. All the six groups of this type give a very specific supramolecular motif through the formation of the $\text{O-H}\cdots\text{O}$ -bonded dimeric associates with $\text{O}\cdots\text{O}$ distances between these carboxyl groups in the range $2.598(8) - 2.660(9)$ Å. Virtually, this hexacarboxyl-terminated macrobicyclic molecule is capable to form the $\text{O-H}\cdots\text{O}$ bonds with six neighboring clathrochelate entities, but, in fact, each of the molecules $\text{Fe}((\text{meta-HOCC}_6\text{H}_4\text{S})_2\text{Gm})_3(\text{Bn-C}_4\text{H}_9)_2$ is H-bonded through two pairs of the $\text{O-H}\cdots\text{O}$ bonds only with three neighboring macrobicycles of this type (Fig. 3, **a**). The distances between the carboxyl groups in *vic*-position of the same macrobicyclic molecule, forming the above clathrochelate dimers are approximately 8.4 Å. Therefore, in the crystal $\text{Fe}((\text{meta-HOCC}_6\text{H}_4\text{S})_2\text{Gm})_3(\text{Bn-C}_4\text{H}_9)_2$, each of its clathrochelate molecules plays a role of the three-connected node that forms the hydrogen-bonded net shown in Fig. 3, **a**. Such three-connected node is able to give only the single type of the three-periodic uninodal edge-transitive net (**srs** in the RCSR terms [25]) and only one type of two-periodic uninodal edge-transitive net with **hcb** (honeycomb) topology. The hydrogen-bonded layers with **hcb** topology, parallel to the crystallographic plane $(1\ 1\ -3)$, are observed in this crystal (Fig. 3, **b**). In general, the structural lability of the above cage molecule may be used for its H-

bonding with a wide range of biological macromolecules containing the H-bond acceptor terminal groups.

General views of one of the two symmetrically independent molecules of the complex $\text{FeBd}_2((\text{meta-HOOC}\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{S})_2\text{Gm})(\text{BF})_2$ are shown in Fig. 4; main geometrical parameters of its clathrochelate framework, as well as those of its two fluoroboron-capped arylsulfide clathrochelate analogs [2], are listed in Table 3. In all their macrobicyclic molecules, the encapsulated metal ion is situated in the centre of its FeN_6 -coordination polyhedron, possessing the geometry intermediate between a trigonal prism (TP, the distortion angle $\varphi = 0^\circ$) and a trigonal antiprism (TAP, $\varphi = 60^\circ$) with the distortion angles φ falling in the range $23.9 - 25.2^\circ$. Such values are very similar to those for their fluoroboron-capped bis- α -benzildioximate analogs with alkylsulfide or S_2 -cyclohexane ribbed substituent(s) ($23.6 - 25.8^\circ$ [2]). Other main geometrical parameters of their cage frameworks are also very similar. In the crystal $\text{FeBd}_2((\text{meta-HOOC}\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{S})_2\text{Gm})(\text{BF})_2$, both symmetrically independent macrobicyclic molecules have much more coplanar orientation of the *meta*- $\text{HOOC}\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{S}$ fragments of their arylsulfide ribbed substituents (the angles between their planar arene fragments are in the range $22.4(2) - 35.2(2)^\circ$) compared to those between the phenyl substituents in its α -benzildioximate chelate moieties varying from $47.20(6)$ to $64.2(1)^\circ$. The former orientation of the *meta*- $\text{HOOC}\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{S}$ substituents is caused by the strong hydrogen bonding between their terminal carboxyl groups, forming a clathrochelate dimer. Besides these H-bonded motifs, the infinite acetone...clathrochelate...acetone...clathrochelate chains, which are parallel to the crystallographic axis *c* and formed by the weak C–H...O and C–H...F hydrogen bondings, were observed in this crystal (Fig. 5). This fact clearly demonstrates a duality of the molecular surface of $\text{FeBd}_2((\text{meta-HOOC}\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{S})_2\text{Gm})(\text{BF})_2$, allowing it to form both the hydrophobic and hydrophilic interactions. We analyzed the external surfaces of the di- and hexacarboxyl-terminated iron(II) clathrochelates using the Hirshfield and Voronoi approaches. For two independent macrobicyclic molecules of $\text{FeBd}_2((\text{meta-$

$\text{HOCC}_6\text{H}_4\text{S})_2\text{Gm})(\text{BF})_2$, from 34.2 to 35.1 and from 58.5 to 59.9% of their molecular Hirshfeld surfaces belong to the H...X hydrogen bonds (X = F, O, S, N) and to the H...H, H... π and π ... π hydrophobic interactions, respectively (Fig. 6). For comparison, in the case of the molecule $\text{Fe}((\text{meta-HOCC}_6\text{H}_4\text{S})_2\text{Gm})_3(\text{Bn-C}_4\text{H}_9)_2$ with six terminal carboxyl groups, 44.1 and 55.9 % of its molecular Hirshfeld surface [26] belong to the hydrophobic and hydrophilic interactions, respectively {Fig. 6, the regions of hydrophilic interactions are mapped on the molecular surfaces in red (the O–H...O hydrogen bonds with the short H...O distances) and in blue (the weak, long-distance, C–H...O interactions)}. The hydrophilic interactions of two independent molecules of $\text{FeBd}_2((\text{meta-HOCC}_6\text{H}_4\text{S})_2\text{Gm})(\text{BF})_2$ and those of the molecule $\text{Fe}((\text{meta-HOCC}_6\text{H}_4\text{S})_2\text{Gm})_3(\text{Bn-C}_4\text{H}_9)_2$, estimated as the molecular surfaces of their Voronoi polyhedra [27], occupy 32.9, 33.8 and 45.8 % of the molecular area, respectively, while from 54.2 to 60.0 % of their Voronoi molecular surfaces belongs to the hydrophobic interactions. The partitioning of the above molecular surfaces within these two methods is very similar; this similarity is earlier reported [28, 29]. Thus, their data suggest that both the hydrophobic and hydrophilic interactions play a key role in the crystal packings of the carboxyl-terminated cage complexes under study.

Conclusions

Thus, we performed *in vitro* testing of a wide range of the iron and cobalt(II) cage complexes as the effectors in the transcription system of DNAP. The inhibitory activities of these mono- and bis-clathrochelates were found to be concentration- and structure-dependent and they are from one to two order of magnitude lower in this system than those in the earlier *in vitro* tested transcription system of RNAP. So, the selectivity of an inhibition of RNA synthesis as compared with that of DNA by the cage complexes under study is observed. Most efficient inhibition in both these systems was observed in the case of the designed iron(II) cage and bis-cage complexes with carboxyl-terminated ribbed substituents, thus suggesting a high impact of the electrostatic (polar) interactions of their terminal carboxyl groups with

the charged and polar side groups of the complimentary aminoacid residues of a protein macromolecule or its macromolecular complexes in the formation of the corresponding host – guest assemblies. The single crystal X-ray experiments for two of these leader clathrochelate transcription inhibitors were performed. All their terminal carboxyl groups were found to be included in the formation of strong hydrogen-bonded clathrochelate-based polymeric associates or of the clathrochelate dimers in their X-rayed crystals. So, their macrobicyclic molecules can form the stable H-bonded assemblies and arrays with various protein macromolecules. The obtained X-ray diffraction data are suitable for further computation studies of the supramolecular “clathrochelate inhibitor – protein (DNAP or RNAP) – nucleic acid (DNA or RNA)” complexes.

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Scheme 1. Chemical drawings of the di- and hexafunctionalized iron(II) clathrochelates under discussion.

Scheme 2. Chemical drawings of the mono- and bis-clathrochelates under study.

Fig. 1. X-ray structure of DNA polymerase from *Thermus aquaticus* [7].

Fig. 2. Side (a) and top (b) views of the molecule $\text{Fe}((\text{meta-HOOC}_6\text{H}_4\text{S})_2\text{Gm})_3(\text{Bn-C}_4\text{H}_9)_2$.

Fig. 3. Hydrogen bonding in the crystal $\text{Fe}((\text{meta-HOCC}_6\text{H}_4\text{S})_2\text{Gm})_3(\text{Bn-C}_4\text{H}_9)_2$ depicted with dashed line (a) and the formation of H-bonded clathrochelate layers with underlying net that is shown with solid black line (b).

Fig. 4. Side (a) and top (b) views of the molecule $\text{FeBd}_2((\text{meta-HOCC}_6\text{H}_4\text{S})_2\text{Gm})(\text{BF})_2$.

Fig. 5. Formation of the C–H...O and C–H...F-bonded chains in the crystal $\text{FeBd}_2((\text{meta-HOCC}_6\text{H}_4\text{S})_2\text{Gm})(\text{BF})_2$ (a) and its packing (b): view along the crystallographic axis a .

Fig. 6. Molecular Hirshfeld surfaces (**b** and **e**) and the fingerprint plots (**c** and **f**) of the molecules $\text{FeBd}_2((\text{meta-HOCC}_6\text{H}_4\text{S})_2\text{Gm})(\text{BF})_2$ (**a**) and $\text{Fe}((\text{meta-HOCC}_6\text{H}_4\text{S})_2\text{Gm})_3(\text{Bn-C}_4\text{H}_9)_2$ (**b**) in their X-rayed crystals. The surfaces are mapped with d_{norm} {the regions with the closest interatomic distances are shown in red (strong interactions) and in blue (weak interactions)}. For the surfaces and fingerprint plots, the regions corresponding to the hydrophilic interactions are highlighted, while the regions corresponding to the hydrophobic interactions are depicted in gray.

Table 1. *In vitro* inhibitory activity of the iron and cobalt(II) mono- and bis-clathrochelates in the transcription systems of T7 RNA and DNA polymerases

Complex	T7 RNAP [5, 9]	DNAP
Monoclathrochelates	IC₅₀ (μM)	
FeBd ₂ ((<i>para</i> -HOOC ₆ H ₄ S) ₂ Gm)(BF) ₂ [8]	0.5 ± 0.1	15 ± 2
FeBd ₂ ((<i>meta</i> -HOOC ₆ H ₄ S) ₂ Gm)(BF) ₂ [8]	0.5 ± 0.1	21 ± 3
FeBd ₂ ((<i>ortho</i> -HOOC ₆ H ₄ S) ₂ Gm)(BF) ₂ [8]		5 ± 1
FeBd ₂ (morphGmSC ₆ H ₄ <i>para</i> -COOH)(BF) ₂ [9]	0.96 ± 0.11	37 ± 4
FeBd ₂ (morphGmSC ₆ H ₄ <i>meta</i> -COOH)(BF) ₂ [9]	0.78 ± 0.08	37 ± 4
FeBd ₂ ((HOOCCH ₂ CH ₂ S) ₂ Gm)(BF) ₂ [8]		25 ± 3
Fe((<i>para</i> -HOOC ₆ H ₄ S) ₂ Gm) ₃ (Bn-C ₄ H ₉) ₂ [8]	0.14 ± 0.02	6 ± 1
Fe((<i>meta</i> -HOOC ₆ H ₄ S) ₂ Gm) ₃ (Bn-C ₄ H ₉) ₂ [8]	0.74 ± 0.08	12 ± 2
Fe((<i>ortho</i> -HOOC ₆ H ₄ S) ₂ Gm) ₃ (Bn-C ₄ H ₉) ₂ [8]	0.50 ± 0.06	20 ± 4
FeBd ₂ (<i>para</i> -HOOC ₆ H ₄ SGmH)(BF) ₂ [8]	0.89 ± 0.13	≥ 100
Fe((HOC ₂ H ₄ S) ₂ Gm) ₃ (Bn-C ₄ H ₉) ₂ [8]		> 100
Fe(PrchGm) ₂ (Cl ₂ Gm)(Bn-C ₄ H ₉) ₂ [10]		> 100
Co(Cl ₂ Gm) ₃ (Bn-C ₄ H ₉) ₂ [11]		20 – 100
Fe((CH ₃ S) ₂ Gm) ₃ (BC ₆ H ₅) ₂ [12]	9.5 ± 0.5	≥ 100
FeBd ₂ (PzOx)(BF) ₂ [13]		≈ 100
FeBd ₂ (CH ₃ N(C ₂ H ₄) ₂ NGmI)(BF) ₂ [14]		≈ 100
FeBd ₂ (morph((HO(CH ₂) ₂ NH)Gm)(BF) ₂ [9]		≈ 100
FeBd ₂ ((4-PyCH ₂ CH ₂ NH) ₂ Gm)(BF) ₂ [14]		≥ 100
FeBd ₂ ((2-PyCH ₂ CH ₂ NH) ₂ Gm)(BF) ₂ [14]		≥ 100
FeBd ₂ Fd(BF) ₂ [15]		≈ 100
CoNx ₃ (BC ₆ H ₄ <i>meta</i> -COOH) ₂ [16]		≈ 100
Bis-clathrochelates		
{FeBd ₂ (<i>meta</i> -HOOC ₆ H ₄ SGm)(BF) ₂ } ₂ [17]	0.43 ± 0.07	25 ± 4
{FeBd ₂ (<i>para</i> -HOOC ₆ H ₄ SGm)(BF) ₂ } ₂ [17]	0.32 ± 0.05	30 ± 4

Table 2. Main geometrical parameters of the *n*-butylboron-capped hexaarylsulfide iron(II) clathrochelates

Parametr	Fe(<i>meta</i> -HOCC ₆ H ₄ S) ₂ Gm) ₃ (Bn-C ₄ H ₉) ₂	^a Fe((PI) ₂ Gm) ₃ (Bn-C ₄ H ₉) ₂ [2]	Fe((CF ₃ C ₆ F ₄ S) ₂ Gm) ₃ (Bn-C ₄ H ₉) ₂ [2]
Fe – N (Å)	1.905(5) – 1.926(6)	1.901(3) – 1.907(3)	1.901(3) – 1.914(3)
B – O (Å)	1.486(10) – 1.522(9) <i>av.</i> 1.505	1.492(5) – 1.518(5) <i>av.</i> 1.508	1.497(4) – 1.514(4) <i>av.</i> 1.508
N – O (Å)	1.334(8) – 1.382(7) <i>av.</i> 1.355	1.363(4) – 1.379(3) <i>av.</i> 1.372	1.353(3) – 1.365(3) <i>av.</i> 1.362
C=N (Å)	1.291(9) – 1.332(10) <i>av.</i> 1.311	1.304(5) – 1.310(5) <i>av.</i> 1.307	1.303(4) – 1.311(4) <i>av.</i> 1.307
C – C (Å)	1.423(11) – 1.453(9) <i>av.</i> 1.437	1.457(5) – 1.476(6) <i>av.</i> 1.463	1.442(4) – 1.448(4) <i>av.</i> 1.446
N=C – C=N (°)	<i>av.</i> 8.0	<i>av.</i> 8.4	<i>av.</i> 8.4
φ (°)	22.8	27.1	25.2
α (°)	79.4	79.2	79.4
h (Å)	2.37	2.32	2.35

Table 3. Main geometrical parameters of the fluoroboron-capped monoribbed-functionilized arylsulfide iron(II) clathrochelates

Parametr	FeBd ₂ ((<i>meta</i> -HOOC ₆ H ₄ S) ₂ Gm)(BF) ₂		^a FeBd ₂ (PlS) ₂ Gm)(BF) ₂ [2]	FeBd ₂ ((PhS) ₂ Gm)(BF) ₂ [2]
	Type A	Type B		
Fe – N (Å)	1.905(4)–1.918(4)	1.908(4)–1.926(4)	1.904(4)–1.926(4)	1.905(3)–1.920(3)
B – O (Å)	1.476(6)–1.497(6) <i>av.</i> 1.489	1.483(7)–1.503(6) <i>av.</i> 1.492	1.477(7) – 1.503(7) <i>av.</i> 1.488	1.468(6) – 1.503(5) <i>av.</i> 1.489
N – O (Å)	1.367(5)–1.377(5) <i>av.</i> 1.372	1.362(5) – 1.371(5) <i>av.</i> 1.367	1.352(4) – 1.376(4) <i>av.</i> 1.366	1.355(4) – 1.373(4) <i>av.</i> 1.365
C=N (Å)	1.294(6)–1.319(6) <i>av.</i> 1.310	1.296(6) – 1.318(5) <i>av.</i> 1.309	1.301(5) – 1.322(5) <i>av.</i> 1.312	1.320(5) – 1.332(5) <i>av.</i> 1.327
C – C (Å)	1.444(7)–1.461(6) <i>av.</i> 1.454	1.436(6)–1.457(6) <i>av.</i> 1.445	1.412(6) – 1.461(6) <i>av.</i> 1.439	1.417(5) – 1.448(6) <i>av.</i> 1.432
N=C – C=N (°)	<i>av.</i> 9.3	<i>av.</i> 11.3	<i>av.</i> 9.6	<i>av.</i> 13.1
φ (°)	25.2	24.4	23.9	25.1
α (°)	78.4	78.6	78.2	79
<i>h</i> (Å)	2.33	2.34	2.33	2.34

Inhibition of DNA synthesis in the transcription system of Taq DNA polymerase by various iron and cobalt(II) tris-dioximate clathrochelates: *in vitro* study and X-ray structure of leader inhibitors, the carboxyl-terminated macrobicyclic complexes

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Iron and cobalt(II) mono- and bis-clathrochelates are effective transcription inhibitors in the system of Taq DNA polymerase.

Series of clathrochelates was *in vitro* tested in the transcription system of Taq DNAP

Bis-carboxyphenylsulfide iron(II) monoclathrochelate has highest inhibitory activity

Lead di and hexacarboxyl clathrochelate inhibitors was studied by X-ray diffraction